

MECHANISMS OF INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE IN
A THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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SUMMARY

The interlaminar fracture toughness of a graphite/polyamide composite laminate was measured by the double cantilever beam test and shown to be eight times higher than that of a typical graphite/epoxy system (AS4/3501-6). The effects of laminate thickness and loading rate were also investigated. Interlaminar fracture mechanisms in thermoplastic matrix composites are associated with extensive matrix deformation around the crack tip. A stretching and cavitation process proceeds in the crack tip plastic zone. This matrix deformation process extends below the crack surfaces, several fiber diameters deep. The extent of matrix deformation depends on the velocity of crack propagation.

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates made from continuous reinforcing fibers and polymer resins have desirable in-plane properties, especially when compared with conventional materials on the basis of property per unit weight. When subjected to out-of-plane loads, however, composite laminates usually perform poorly. Interlaminar cracks appear and delaminate the composite structure. Although applications that involve direct out-of-plane loads are rare and can be avoided by proper design procedures, delamination remains one of the major concerns in composite applications. The reason is that, whenever delamination occurs, it also affects many in-plane properties such as bending stiffness and compressive strength. The improvement of delamination resistance in composite laminates is therefore an important subject of research.

Interlaminar cracks propagate through the resin phase between fiber bundles or along fiber/resin interfaces. The toughness of the resin therefore plays an important role in resisting delamination. One method of increasing delamination resistance is to improve the toughness of existing epoxy resins [1]. Another method is to use other polymer resins that are inherently tough but also possess some of the desirable physical and mechanical properties of epoxy. During the last few years, much interest has been generated in the use of high-performance thermoplastic resins as the matrix material for advanced composites. Polyphenyl sulfone [2], polyetheretherketone [3,4], polyphenylene sulfide [5], and amorphous polyimide [6] were the subjects of many recent studies.

In this study, we investigated the interlaminar fracture characteristics of a graphite fiber composite laminate with a thermoplastic polyamide copolymer as the matrix resin. The resin is referred to as J-polymer. The neat resin properties of J-polymer were reported by Chang [7], some of which are listed in Table I.

TABLE I. Properties of J-polymer Neat Resin

Specific gravity	1.04
Glass transition temperature	145 °C
Melt temperature	285 °C
Young's modulus	320 ksi (2206 MPa)
Flex modulus	244 ksi (1682 MPa)
Shear modulus	144 ksi (993 MPa)
Tensile strength	10 ksi (69 MPa)
Maximum elongation	58 %

CHARACTERIZATION OF MODE-I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

SAMPLE PREPARATION

The double cantilever beam (DCB) test [8] was used to characterize interlaminar fracture toughness. Unidirectional AS4/J-polymer prepreg tapes, 0.005 inch thick, made from a Du Pont melt-impregnation process were used to fabricate the test laminates. A matched-mold molding process was used in this study, although the prepreg tapes are already fully impregnated and can be used in an in-situ lamination process. An 1-inch-wide Teflon®-coated glass fabric was placed at midplane along one edge of the laminate to initiate cracking. The molding was performed at 300°C, 1200 psi with a 6X6-inch steel mold. The process was completed after the mold cooled down to room temperature under pressure. Laminates were also made from AS4/3501-6 epoxy for comparison tests. These laminates were fabricated by Composites Technology Associates, Inc., with a vacuum bag and autoclave process. Laminates of 12, 24, 36, and 48 layers were fabricated and cut into 1-inch-wide test specimens. The final DCB specimen assembly is shown in Figure 1.

TESTING

The characterization of Mode-I fracture toughness was carried out in an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine. The tests were conducted at constant crosshead speed of 0.5 and 0.1 inch/min. Our previous experience shows that the results obtained at these test rates are identical to tests conducted in the load feedback control mode. To monitor the crack front position, the edge of the sample was painted white and scratched with markings at 0.0285-inch spacings. A video camera equipped with a microscope lens was used to monitor crack propagation. The video image was mixed with real-time data acquired from a computer data acquisition system when recorded on video tapes (Figure 2). Slow-speed playback of the video tape shows frame-by-frame advancement

Figure 1. DCB specimen.

Figure 2. Simultaneous video recording of crack event and measurement data.

of the crack front, along with instantaneous load and displacement data. This method is useful in estimating the velocity of crack propagation.

RESULTS

Typical loading-unloading curves for the AS4/J-polymer and AS4/3501-6 epoxy are compared in Figure 3. The two representative test specimens are comparable in initial crack length and the amount of crack extension. The crack extension process in the AS4/J-polymer laminate shows some "stick-slip" type of behavior, indicated by the jagged load-displacement curve, whereas the crack propagation in the AS4/epoxy is stable. The critical load required to propagate the crack in the AS4/J-polymer laminate is 2 to 3 times higher than that required for the AS4/epoxy laminate. This 2-3X critical load ratio is independent of crack length and is consistently observed for tests conducted at two different loading rates and the four different laminate thicknesses (Figure 4).

The interlaminar fracture toughness represented by the Mode-I critical strain energy release rate -- G_{IC} , is calculated from integrating the area enclosed by the loading-unloading curve. The results are shown in Figure 5 and Table II. The G_{IC} measured for both materials is independent of crack length, loading rate (0.1 and 0.5 inch/min), and laminate thickness. The average G_{IC} is 11.5 lbf/inch (2732 N/m) for AS4/J-polymer, and 1.5 lbf/inch (356 N/m) for AS4/3501-6 epoxy. We found that thicker laminates are better suited for testing thermoplastic matrix laminates; the large geometric displacement induced in the thinner laminates (12 and 24 layers) sometimes causes failure in the adhesive joints between the laminate and the aluminum tab.

Figure 3. Representative DCB loading-unloading curves of AS4/3501-6 epoxy and AS4/J-polymer.

Figure 4. Critical load for interlaminar fracture of AS4/3501-6 epoxy and AS4/J-polymer at test speeds of (a) 0.1 inch/min and (b) 0.5 inch/min.

Figure 5. G_{IC} of AS4/3501-6 epoxy and AS4/J-polymer at test speeds of (a) 0.1 inch/min and (b) 0.5 inch/min. Legends are the same as in Figure 4.

TABLE II. Interlaminar Fracture Toughness -- G_{IC}

Sample Type		Test Rate (inch/min)	G_{IC} (avg.) (lbf/inch) (kN/m)	
AS4/E	12 layers	0.1	1.582	0.376
AS4/E	24 layers	0.1	1.446	0.343
AS4/E	36 layers	0.1	1.433	0.340
AS4/E	48 layers	0.1	1.663	0.395
AS4/E	12 layers	0.5	1.296	0.308
AS4/E	24 layers	0.5	1.636	0.389
AS4/E	36 layers	0.5	1.500	0.356
AS4/E	48 layers	0.5	1.651	0.392
AS4/J	12 layers	0.1	11.401	2.708
AS4/J	24 layers	0.1	14.516	3.448
AS4/J	36 layers	0.1	10.614	2.521
AS4/J	48 layers	0.1	10.531	2.501
AS4/J	12 layers	0.5	---	---
AS4/J	24 layers	0.5	12.104	2.875
AS4/J	36 layers	0.5	10.634	2.526
AS4/J	48 layers	0.5	10.447	2.481

Average value:

AS4/3501-6 epoxy: 1.5 lbf/inch (0.362 kN/m)
AS4/J-polymer: 11.5 lbf/inch (2.723 kN/m)

The rate of crack propagation was measured by reviewing the video tape with simultaneously recorded crack events and quantitative data. The crack propagation rates in AS4/J-polymer and AS4/3501-epoxy are compared in Figure 6. The crack propagation rate in AS4/epoxy is relatively constant and is about 6 times faster than that in AS4/J-polymer. The unstable crack propagation rate in AS4/J-polymer produces different types of fracture feature on the fracture surface. Figure 7 shows a narrow band of "smooth" fracture feature extending through the entire width of a specimen. The figure also shows the rate of crack extension as the crack propagates through this region. The "smooth" fracture feature is associated with the sudden increase in crack propagation rate. Several AS4/J-polymer specimens were split apart at high speed at the end of the tests; the entire fractured surface was found to be made up of the "smooth" fracture feature. At the regular test speeds (0.1 and 0.5 inch/min), the smooth fracture features are few and seldom span the entire width of the specimen. Therefore, we conclude that the different fracture features produced on the fractured surface are the results of sudden changes in local crack propagation rate and are not caused by local variations in material properties.

Figure 6. Comparison of crack propagation rate in AS4/3501-6 and AS4/J-polymer.

Figure 7. Sudden changes in crack propagation rate create different fracture features.

FRACTURE MECHANISMS

FRACTOGRAPHY STUDY

Mode-I interlaminar fractures in AS4/epoxy and AS4/J-polymer are controlled by very different deformation and fracture mechanisms. The AS4/3501-6 epoxy exhibits typical brittle fracture, which is represented by the mirror-smooth fracture surfaces through the resins or fiber/resin interfaces (Figure 8). On the other hand, extensive matrix deformation was involved in the interlaminar fracture of AS4/J-polymer. Resins surrounding the fibers experience extensive stretching before the two matching fracture surfaces separate (Figure 9). The extensive matrix deformation is not limited to fracture surfaces. It is also evident several fiber diameters deep below the fracture plane (Figure 10). The few resin-rich areas between fibers show the type of ductile fracture dimples created by void nucleation and growth (Figure 11).

Adhesion between the J-polymer and the AS4 graphite fiber is good. Resins peeled off from the fibers only after they were stretched extensively (Figure 12). Further evidence of good interfacial adhesion is found on the "smooth" fracture surfaces created by a high crack propagation rate (Figure 13). The crack propagates only through the resins, not the resin/fiber interfaces. The few broken fibers that protruded from the fracture surface all show complete resin coverage over their surfaces. The amount of resin deformation in these "smooth" fracture surfaces is small.

Figure 8. Fracture surface of AS4/3501-6 epoxy shows typical brittle fracture.

Figure 9. Fracture surface of AS4/J-polymer shows extensive resin deformation before fracture.

Figure 10. Extensive matrix deformation is also found at several fiber diameters deep below the fracture plane.

Figure 11. Fracture surface in resin rich areas between fibers shows typical ductile fracture features.

Figure 12. Resins peeled off from fibers after extensive stretching.

Figure 13. Fracture surface produced by fast crack propagation. No indication of fiber/matrix separation.

FRACTURE MODEL

Figure 14 shows a physical model constructed to describe the deformation and fracture mechanisms involved in the Mode-I interlaminar fracture of thermoplastic matrix composites. The high stress intensity at the crack tip produces a plastic zone in front of the crack tip. The plastic zone in brittle epoxy matrix systems remains a continuum and conserves its volume before the crack propagates into the plastic zone. In ductile thermoplastic matrix systems, the activities in front of the crack tip are more complex. Inside the plastic zone, and immediately in front of the crack tip, voids are nucleating and expanding as the crack front advances towards the plastic zone. Areas where resins are still connected continue to stretch and elongate into ligaments that bridge the yet-to-be-separated fracture surfaces. This region where the resins are no longer a continuum, is called the deformation process zone. The exact location of the crack tip is not well defined. However, we define the boundary between the opened crack fissure and the deformation process zone as the location of the "apparent crack tip", which we believe represents the crack tip position measured in our fracture tests.

The deformation process zone and the plastic zone ahead of it extend to some depth below the fracture plane and are subjected to heavy constraints from nearby fibers and the elastic body outside (the bulk of the laminate). As the crack propagates through the deformation process zone in the plane of fracture, the highly "porous" deformation zone in the adjacent planes will undergo an unloading process. This unloading process, characterized by large displacements and volume contractions, is quite different from the unloading of the plastic zone - an elastoplastic continuum, in the case of graphite/epoxy. Resins in the porous deformation process zone away from the major crack plane are also subjected to shear loads induced by the cantilever beam action. In a few tests, we noticed that some microcracks nucleated at adjacent planes ahead of the major crack front. These microcracks will extend slightly when the nearby major crack passes by.

Figure 14. A physical model of interlaminar fracture in thermoplastic matrix composite laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

The Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of a polyamide matrix composite laminate was found to be significantly higher than that of traditional epoxy matrix composites. The extensive deformation in the thermoplastic resins accounts for the large amount of energy dissipated during crack propagation. The response of the thermoplastic resin to fracture is affected by the local and/or average crack propagation rate. A physical model was suggested to describe the mechanisms involved in crack propagation through the polyamide matrix. The general applicability of the model to other thermoplastic systems has yet to be confirmed. Existing mathematical fracture mechanics models that apply to linear elastic matrix systems will have to be modified to accommodate the anelastic behavior of the thermoplastic resins and the complex crack tip activities involved in the fracture process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks are due to Messrs. G. A. Crolla, R. A. Pazdalski, B. M. Moran, and J. F. Pedrick for their assistance in conducting this study.

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